

Lexical Choices and Artistic Vision in Selected Poems of Paul Laurence Dunbar and Langston Hughes

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Abstract

This article investigates the lexical choices and artistic vision of two African American poets, Paul Laurence Dunbar and Langston Hughes. The two poets are representatives of two eras in the history of African American literature. Dunbar represents the reconstruction era while Langston Hughes represents the Renaissance era. The article aims at revealing how the lexical choices made by the two poets in the articulation of their creative concerns are predicated upon their artistic visions. The justification of this study lies in the fact that the employment of a particular language choice, in this case, *Ebonics*, by the two poets is informed by their artistic impulses. The significance of the study is that the Black English allows the artists and their audience the opportunity of capturing the experiences of the blacks. The article adopts the postcolonial theory of art and lexical semantics which is an aspect of structural linguistics in the interrogation of the topic. Through the utilization of the qualitative research methodology, the study comes out with the findings that the artistic vision of the two poets is the assertion of black identity and that the use of *Ebonics* is a deliberate attempt at excluding non- African Americans. It is intended to give both the writers and the readers that distinct identity that sets the Blacks apart as a unique group of people in the American society. The study recommends that further studies should be carried out on the style of African American poets beyond the Renaissance period vis-a-vis their artistic visions.

Key words: Self-assertion, artistic vision, Ebonics, Postcolonialism, Lexical semantics, etc.

Résumé

Cet article examine les choix lexicaux et la vision artistique de deux poètes afro-américains, Paul Laurence Dunbar et Langston Hughes. Les deux poètes sont les représentants de deux époques dans l'histoire de la littérature afro-américaine. Dunbar représente l'époque de la reconstruction tandis que Langston Hughes représente celle de la Renaissance. L'article vise à montrer comment les choix lexicaux faits par les deux poètes dans l'articulation de leurs préoccupations créatives reposent sur leurs visions artistiques. La justification de cette étude réside dans le fait que l'emploi d'un choix de langue particulière, dans ce cas, *Ebonics*, l'anglais afro-américain, par les deux poètes est informé par leurs impulsions artistiques. L'importance de l'étude est que le black permet aux artistes et à leur public de capturer les expériences des Noirs. L'article adopte la théorie postcoloniale de l'art et de la sémantique lexicale qui est un aspect de la linguistique structurale pour examiner le sujet. Grâce à l'utilisation de la méthodologie de recherche qualitative, l'étude révèle que la vision artistique des deux poètes est l'affirmation de l'identité noire et que l'utilisation d'anglais afro-américain est une tentative délibérée pour exclure les Américains non-africains. Il est

destiné à donner aux écrivains ainsi qu'aux lecteurs cette identité distincte qui distingue les Noirs comme un groupe unique de personnes dans la société américaine. L'étude recommande que d'autres études soient menées sur le style des poètes afro-américains au-delà de la période de la Renaissance par rapport à leurs visions artistiques.

Mots-Clés : Affirmation de soi, Vision artistique, *Ebonics*, Postcolonialisme, Sémantique lexicale

Introduction

Poetry is one of the earliest forms of artistic creations ever recorded by the slaves in America culminating into what is called African American poetry. It is a literature that encapsulates the experiences of the Africans in the American society. This literature began to evolve in the early days of their slavery in the new world and basically had as its raw materials the African lore and customs from where they were forcefully uprooted. At the outset of the creative ingenuity of the African Americans, the racial hegemony that existed between the Black and White races was not favourable to the blacks. In fact the racial Whites referred to their artistic endeavours then as the unintelligent scribbling of the Blacks. Nevertheless, this literature has always been imbued with the distinct yearnings of the black man in the new world. These yearnings were their desires to be free from the racial bottlenecks that were placed on them by the Whites, to be reunited with their root again, to have a distinct identity that was not dictated by the racial White, etc.

Right from this early stage, the literature of the African Americans was faced with a plethora of obstacles. First, the racial Whites did not believe that any African was intelligent enough to create literature worthy of critical attention. Also, even when they began to be noticed, there were rules that were instituted by the racial whites to stifle any creative and resistant impulses that were perceived to be anti-racial. Hence, if the literature was seen to be racially inflammatory, it will not be accepted by a publishing house and therefore will not be published. So, the early African American writers like Phillis Wheatley, Lucy Terry, Frederick Douglass Olaudah Equiano Harriet Jacobs etc, had to manipulate the language and the Christian metaphors to still pass across their message to their audience. They had to use the language of their enslavers in a creative way to have their agitations aired. Concerning this, Patricia Hill notes that:

... it is to their credit that African Americans produced and published a body of literature by using the language and professed religious beliefs of their enslavers while often simultaneously protesting their enslavement....To be certified as safe, non-inflammatory authorities, they were obliged to imitate European genres (neoclassical poetry and prose, sermons and formal letters) and to incorporate biblical rhetoric and symbolism in stating their political objectives. But these restrictions also allowed them to covertly communicate (usually through masters or missionaries reading to slave audience) with other slaves, who no doubt well understood embedded meanings, simultaneously allowing them to convict the conscience of white people (3-4)

This paper focuses on the lexical choices made by the two poets and how their choices of lexical items give credence to their artistic vision. Basically, the emphasis will be on the use of Ebonics by the two poets. The artistic vision of the two poets seems to be the same: that of the assertion of the black self and identity in the American society. Paul Laurence Dunbar and Langston Hughes wrote during the reconstruction and the renaissance eras respectively. These periods witnessed the growth of self-awareness and resistance within the corpus of African American literature. The reconstruction was a period that set out to reconstruct, re-order and dissolve the differences that existed between the Whites and the Blacks. This period witnessed the agitations of the Blacks being aired, though not in an assertive way as in the Renaissance. It was during this period that Booker T. Washington wrote his famous *Up From Slavery* which focuses on this issue. Whereas the early writers were majorly implicating the metaphors of the Christian religion and impregnating them with the sensibilities of their resistance impulses, Dunbar and Hughes went beyond this to create a new linguistic device -- Ebonics in order to strategically and overtly resist the racial hegemony of the Whites. The utilization of this tool, Ebonics, is to allow the African American writer, and indeed, the entire African Americans the opportunity of redefining themselves and creating a unique identity for themselves. The fact is that the African Americans may not be able to outsmart their captors by using the parameters for communication (Standard American English) instituted and enshrined by the same people who have enslaved them. Ebonics therefore, affords them an option in attacking the racial hegemony of the Whites in the American society.

After the reconstruction, there was a flowering period in the African American literary landscape that is generally referred to as the Harlem Renaissance (1920s-1940s). This period witnessed the outburst of artistic and creative ingenuity from the African Americans. It was a period of great self-assertion without any iota of fear and timidity. It was marked by artistic radicalism and resistance to White racial hegemony. The assertion of the African American unique identity is succinctly captured by Langston Hughes when he notes in his famous essay "The Negro Artist and The Racial Mountain" that:

But, to my mind, it is the duty of the younger Negro artist, if he accepts any duties at all from outsiders, to change through the force of his art that old whispering "I want to be white" hidden in the aspiration of his people... We younger Negro artists who create now intend to express our individual dark-skinned selves without fear or shame. If white people are pleased we are glad. If they are not, it doesn't matter. We know we are beautiful. And ugly too. (1271).

The two poets under study are African Americans. Both of them wrote about the White racial hegemony in the American society. However, they wrote at different eras. Whereas Dunbar wrote during the reconstruction era, Langston Hughes wrote during the renaissance period. Both of them handle the issue of racism and self-assertion differently in terms of their approach. Whereas Dunbar adopts a subtle approach in addressing the issue,

Langston Hughes adopts a more radical approach. Nevertheless, what they have in common is the manipulation of the lexis of the English language and the utilization of Ebonics. Both of them use a combination of the Standard English and the Black English.

This study adopts the postcolonial theory and structural linguistics in the interrogation of the topic. Postcolonial theory is often used to interrogate the literature of those who have been exposed to colonialism, imperialism and racism basically to see the level of the influence of the imperial, colonial and racial forces on the colonised state. For the African Americans, their contact with these forces was not first and foremost in their home, Africa, but in the new world where they were taken to. This kind of colonialism is what Robert J. C. Young calls “migratory colonialism”. Frantz Fanon’s *Black Skin White Masks* gives a detailed explication of the causes and effects of colonialism, imperialism and racism on the Black people. With reference to Fanon’s views, I have stated elsewhere that: “Fanon notes that the major cause of racism on the Blacks is the inferiority complex on the part of the racial whites. This inferiority is at the level of sexuality. He notes that the white man finds himself sexually inferior to the black man and therefore sets out to debase and exterminate him through racism”. (20). Consequently, the Blacks’ experience of forced migration slavery, racism, imperialism, denial of rights and privileges, and their exploitation by the racial Whites are all tempers and ethos of colonialism. Fanon’s solution to the problem seems to be different from those that are proposed by other writers like Young and Homi Bhabha. Whereas the duo propose hybridity (345), Fanon seems to propose the destruction of mental colonization. (9).

This research agrees with and chooses to follow the position of Robert J. C. Young- hybridization. We tend to agree with Young that you cannot fight colonialism with the instrument invented and utilised by its proponents- violence. In this research, the justification for our position is that you cannot beat your master. If violence was invented and utilized by the colonialist in the pursuit of his objectives, then its destruction seems problematic if not impossible if we still rely on violence for its destruction. We agree with Young that hybridity seems to appeal more and have promises of objective achievement. So, what is this hybridity all about? It is the turning, twisting, breaking, reforming and colouring of the resources of colonialism with the nuances of the folk knowledge, ideologies and cultural objectives. Young believes that the answer lies;

.... in the creation of a counter-modernity through the transformative potential of the transculturations of gender and hybridity, creating new traditions that will not be a return to an imaginary pure, indigenous knowledge but a repertoire drawn from a dialectical mixture of classical and folk knowledge, the pure and the mixed, the high and the low, the masculine and the feminine: modernity hybridized. (345).

What we have today as the African American culture is the hybridity of the influences of the two cultures- African and American. To discountenance the fact that there is no African influence in today’s African American culture is to tow the path of error in scholarship. On this issue, Ushie Godwin notes;

contrary to these prejudices that perpetrated falsehood, it has been found out by those who objectively and methodically studied African cultures back in the continental base and on the transplanted ground as well as present day practices, even among whites that both the Blacks and Whites have been influenced by the black presence and tradition in the area of religion, secular life, artistic culture, music, folklore and language. denying retentions of African elements in the evolved culture of the African American is more farcical than real, an attempt to peddle falsity.(188)

Within the context of African American literature and poetry as our genre of interrogation, focus is going to basically be on the resistant struggle for freedom and self-assertion, the triumph of black culture and individuality as well as the persistence on the side of the Blacks for their rights and distinct self even after the emancipation proclamation in America. As we said earlier, this research attempts to trace the struggles that come with the force migration colonialism and how such struggles has paid off today in relation to the achievement of the objectives. We think that post-colonialism will be the right theory for such interrogation for as Young puts it;

Postcolonialism is defined by this particular combination of historical practice extended into a politics of translation design to transform the conditions of the present. Its key issues include the colonial, imperial and anti-colonial past, the post-colonial present, the international division of labour (starting with child labour), peoples' and cultural rights, emigration and immigration, force migration and migrancy, nomadism, settlement and diaspora in both western and tricontinental societies. (66).

From the foregoing, it is evident that postcolonialism has some relationship with psychoanalysis. Apart from this, post-colonialism also holds some connections with other theories like Marxism, new historicism, structuralism and post structuralism, modernism and postmodernism, multiculturalism, feminism. It also holds a relationship with new historicism in its insistence on the "cultural experience of the marginalized". Culture in this context is the "representation of (the) experience" of the colonized people. Postcolonialism is oftentimes traced to Frantz Fanon's study of race relation in his work *Black Skin, White Masks*. However, it was Edward Said that developed it into an academic discipline. Other proponents of this theory include Homi Bhabha, Ahmed, Amin, Appiah, Chakrabarty, Spivak and of course and none the least Robert J.C. Young.

Structural linguistic is another theory that is utilised, though sparingly in this paper. Our emphasis is on lexical semantics. Structural linguistics is traced to Ferdinand de Saussure. He holds that linguistic units generate their meaning from the relationship they hold with each other within a self-contained system. Lexical semantics focuses on the meaning of lexical items or word. Lekan Oyeleye quotes Marclaury thus: "Marclaury defines lexical semantics as the analysis of linguistic meaning among words, affixes and stick phrases especially of the semantic relations that integrate such lexical items into system domain conventional image or discourse." (137). Also, Timothy Baldwin defines it as "the study of what individual lexical items mean, why they mean what they do, how we

can represent all of this, and where the combined interpretation for an utterance comes from”(<http://www.cs.mu.oz.au/research/lt/nlp06/materials/Baldwin/intro.pdf>). Apart from de Saussure, other proponents of structural linguistics include; Gilbert Lazard. Matthews, Peter.Etc.

Ebonics as a Linguistic Variant in Selected Poems of Paul Laurence Dunbar

Paul Laurence Dunbar’s poetry seems to be largely composed in the African American dialect. The reason for this is not far-fetched. Many of his poems in Standard English were often rejected by publishers. They often returned such poems to him with a letter demanding a dialect poem from him. The question then is: what is African American dialect and what is its place and relevance in the poetry of Paul Dunbar? What came to be known as African American dialect is a product of the hybridity of the different African languages that converged in the New World after the Cross Atlantic Slave Trade. It is a given that the Africans taken across the Atlantic during the slave trade were not from the same origin in terms of culture and linguistic peculiarities. Given these differences, there was need for communication and what came to be the linguistic vehicle for communication among the slaves is what has been referred to as Ebonics. This language has been referred to severally by different groups. For some it is Black Vernacular English. To others it is African American vernacular English, Black English vernacular, Ebonics, Black American English, Creole, etc.

For Paul Dunbar and others who utilize the dialect form in their creative composition, Ebonics is that language that possesses the ability to accommodate the African ethos and ideological peculiarities. This variant has been greatly argued to be a language in its own right and not a dialect of the English language. In Dunbar’s poems, some of the features observable of this medium are that if it is used with standard English, the positive word(s) or phrases are written in Ebonics while the racial or seemingly negative word(s) or phrases are in standard English. We can find this in; “Antebellum sermon”; (28) e.g.

Ebonics

My brothahs(stanza1),
Words of comfo’t,(stanza1)
To each othah,(stanza1)
Hebrew chillum, (stanza 2)
scriptuah,(stanza 7)
bref,(*breath*) (stanza 7)

Standard English

distress,(stanza1),refuse,(stanza3)
enemies,(stanza 4),

In “A corn song”, this peculiarity is observable in the chorus of the poem while the stanzas are in Standard English.

Other peculiarities observable about this language are in the aspect of phonology and orthography. Something that seems to stand out clear is the fact that Ebonics does not have a universal orthographic system. In other words, writers seem to write based on the spelling that they are conversant with or the one that appeals most to them. For example, “my” could be spelt as “mah” or “ma” by the same author depending on the environment or

his mood at the point of composition. These features are seen in the poems of Dunbar analysed in this work.

In “An ante-bellum sermon”, we have the following examples;

Replacement of r and er with a ah, u’ etc

“Hyeah” for “here”,

Wildaness for wilderness,

Othah for other

Fo for for

fu’ for for

sez for says

houah for hour

thundah for thunder

Ouah for our

Foolin’ for fooling

Scriptuah for scripture

Lawd for lord

Ef for if

O’ for of

Omission of the final consonant sound(s)

Apart from the orthographical peculiarities that we have observed above, other distinctive features of Ebonics as a linguistic variant are observable in the fact that some words are spelt and hence pronounced without the final consonant sound. We can find evidence of this in “an ante-bellum sermon”. Thus:

An’	and
Subjic’	subject
Wukin’	working
Foolin’	fooling
Aroun’	around
Sen’	send
Lan’	land
Blas’	blast
Worl’	world
Fas’	fast
Citiz--	citizen
From “When Malindy sings” we have;	
Tellin’	telling
Jes’	just
Stan’	stand
Los’	lost
Fin’	find
Sof’	soft
From “The party” we have;	

Fou'	four
Las'	last
Fu'	for
Mus'	must
Mo'	more
O'	of
Hol'	hold
From "A back- log song" we have;	
Bigges'	biggest
Erroun'	around
Soun'	sound
Ol'	old
Feas'	feast
Leas'	least

Another feature of Ebonics is **the omission or the substitution of (a) medial sound(s)**.

Examples of this in "An ante-bellum sermon" are;

Comfo't	comfort
Co'n	corn
Lawd	lord
Wuth	worth
Ha'f	half
Isrul	Israel
Gab'el's	Gabriel's

From "Lonesome" we have;

Ag'n	again
Some'n'	something
Sence	since
Durn	damn

From "When Malindy sings" we have;

Sta't	start
Lak	like
F'om	from
O'gan	organ
Whut	what
Draps	drops
Edicated	educated

From "The party" we have;

Pahty	party
Sich	such
Set	sit
Sot	sat
Shet	shot

Phonologically, Ebonics also has the feature of **the pronunciation of 'th' as 'f', 'd', 't', etc or non pronunciation at all**. Examples of this from "an ante-bellum sermon include;

Dah	there
De	the
Dis	this
Bref	breath
Dat	that
Dese	these
Wif	with

From “Lonesome” we have;

‘n	than
‘em	them

From “When Malindy sings” we have;

Mouf	mouth
Den	then

From “The party” we have;

Dough	though
Bofe	both
Dier	their

Ebonics also has the peculiarity of the **dropping of the first syllable of some di- or multi syllabic words**. Examples of this are;

From “An ante-bellum sermon”;

‘splain	explain
‘cause	because
‘bout	about
‘sail	assail

From “When Malindy sings” we have;

‘nough	enough
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From “the party” we have;

‘mence	commence
‘fect	affect
‘scuse	excuse
‘pologisin’	apologizing
‘ginst	against

Compound words / coinages is another feature of Ebonics

From “When Malindy sings” we have;

G’way	go away
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Timid-lak-a-drawin’ neah

From “the party” we have;

a-bowin’ an’ a-swayin’ an’ a-swingin’
which-a-way

Grammatical and syntactic deviation is another feature of Ebonics.

Examples of this from “An ante-bellum sermon” are;

- We *isgathahedhyeah* , my brothahs
- An’ *we* chooses fu’ ouahsubjc’
- An’ ef he *refuse* to do it

- Dat/’s preachin’ discontent
- ‘cause I *isn’t*; I’s e a – judgin’
- I’s e-a-givin’ you de scriptuah
- I’s e-a- handin’ you de fac’s
- an’ dahsothah*thinks*lakpher’oh
- when *we*’sereco’nisedezcitiz’--

from “The party” we have;

- evahbody dressed dier fines
- sencelas’quah’tlymeetin’ day
- now who you askin’
- you’s got to break de line
- I won’t tell you nothin’ mo’
- S’pose you’d been an’ seed it all;
- But I’s done my bes’ to suit you
- We wasmos’ nigh stuffed to def!
- ‘twelldah was n’tnothin’ lef
- Tom, he knowed how we’d be feelin’

From “A back-log song” we have;

- An’ de young folks, males an’ misses *is* a- tryin’
- De chicken ain’t so trus’ful as dey*was*
- An’ de wise ol’ hens *is*roostin’ mighty high

The first question to ask particularly about this last peculiarity of Ebonics is – what makes it ungrammatical or syntactically wrong? The major error underscored in the examples immediately above is the error of concord. Many of the examples use plural verbs for singular subjects and vice versa. Another error is the error that arises from the wrong use of the inflected variant of the modal auxiliary “be”. We have instances where “is” is used in place of “am”, “was” in place of “were” and “is” in place of “are”. We also find instances where the modal auxiliary is totally absent. – “now who you askin’”. We equally notice the error of double negation. – “I won’t tell you nothin’ mo’”.

The second question will be- what is the place of these peculiarities in the overall thematic occupation of the poems? First, we may not be totally wrong to assert that the poet’s choice of the black dialect is an unequivocal rejection of the tradition of the racial Whites as well as an assertive step toward the blacks’ distinct identity and individuality. Again, looking at the last peculiarity- grammatical and syntactic deviation, we refuse to view such deviation at the surface level. Within such deviation is an overt sign and code with semantic impulses. Looking at the first two examples, we discover that the first person plural pronoun subjects are taking singular verbs- “is” and “chooses”. This is not haphazard. It is intended to assert the singularity of the African American community in purpose and dreams. Conversely, in the third example, the third person singular pronoun used for pharaoh is actually plural in ideology. This is why the poet uses a plural verb- “refuse” instead of “refuses”. By doing this, it seems the poet intends to posit that “he” is a representative one for the entire racial Americans. The same is applicable to “an’ dahsothahs thinks lakpher’oh” (and there are others who think like pharaoh). From the foregoing it is

clear that the utilization of Ebonics is targeted at asserting the African American distinct identity.

Lexical Choices and their Implications in selected poems of Langston Hughes

For the effective execution of his duty, the poet must select his lexical items properly. Failure in this aspect may lead to the failure of the entire creative enterprise. The question is often asked and serious debate has often come up as to whether a poet must necessarily subject the creative muse to the choice of the vehicles that must carry such muse. In other words, must the poet search for the right lexical item before birthing forth his creative ingenuity? Many believe that if a poet is too conscious of the lexical item to be used, he may forfeit bringing forth the spirit of the muse. However, we believe that what makes a poet a poet is not the singing of a song in a clumsy manner nor the telling of a tale in an esoteric tongue but the speaking of the minds of the spirit in an elegant and beautiful way befitting the spirit. So the choice of appropriate words with the non-sacrificing of the spirit's mind therefore seem to be one of the core cardinal features of a poet's identity. The right choice of words is like a design of gold set in a collection of wood. The right choice of words brings the split between the Jesus and Paul and the seven sons of Scevas. This position is what Geoffrey Leech avers when he posits: "looking at the might- have- been of stylistic variation is the way of making the illusive quality of good writing open to inspection"(133).

Considering the poetry of Langston Hughes, one readily sees some lexical choices resonating. These repetitions are not just haphazard but they carry in them the poet's message. For example such lexical items as song and story keep reoccurring in many of his poems here studied. In "Aunt Sue's stories", the reader is introduced to these items in the first stanza:

Aunt Sue has a head full of stories
Aunt Sue has a whole heart full of stories
Summer nights on the front porch
Aunt Sue cuddles a brown-face child to her bosom
And tell him stories

"Stories" could be experiences of one's life or those of others. By using this item, therefore, Hughes implicates that the African Americans have experiences to tell to the younger generation and the world at large. The validity of this assertion is seen in the third stanza when the poet persona avers;

And the dark- faced child, listening
Knows that aunt Sue's stories are real stories
He knows that Aunt Sue never got her stories
Out of any book at all
But that they came
Right out of her own life

The kind of stories this character has to tell is further expanded in "Mother to Son". The persona in this poem begins by saying: "well son I'll tell you:" while that of "The Negro Mother" begins by saying: "children, I come back today/ to tell you a story of the long dark way". The question is: how does this relate to African American self-assertion? Stories are often told for some purposes. They are at the surface told for leisure or pleasure,

but at the epicenter of storytelling is the intention of informing, educating, or moralizing etc. By using such lexical items therefore, the poet and his persona assert their intention overtly. This intention is to tell the entire African Americans of who they are, where they have been, what they have passed through, where they are going and how they can get there.

In “Aunt Sue’s stories”, the poet-persona provides a panoramic view of the story of the Blacks in America. However, it is in “Mother to Son” and “The Negro Mother” that the details are given.

In “Mother to Son”, there are other lexical choices that give vent to the kind of stories the African Americans tell. Such lexical items like “crystal stair”, “tacks”, “splinters”, “no carpet on the floor”, “bare”, “turning corners”, “goin’ in the dark”, “don’t you turn back”, “don’t you fall now” etc demand some degree of interrogation. The persona begins by saying: “Life for me ain’t been no crystal stair”. To climb a stair is not easy, but if one is strong, one can climb a crystal stair. A crystal stair here is a stair that is devoid of obstacles, barriers and injurious objects. For the persona, it is not a question of climbing a crystal stair but that which is characterized by tacks, splinters etc. Tacks and splinters are sharp objects that can easily injure. For the persona to say that the stairs he has been climbing “had tacks in it/ and splinters” is a pointer to the delicate nature of the move to the African American dream. Tacks and splinters are sharp nails or broken bottles that sometimes if one do not look closely, may not see. Yet, these are the things that characterize the stairs that the black man must climb. Would there have been any difference if the poet had said:

Life for me ain’t been no stair
It is a stair with barriers. (Mine)

The answer is yes. “Barriers” suggest things that can be easily seen. But the use of “tacks” and “splinters” suggest not mere barriers but very delicate barriers. Of course, this is true of the African American move toward self-assertion and actualization. They had to contend with racism in all the facets of life. These were very delicate tacks and splinters as they could easily injure and kill them and, indeed, killed some of the Negroes. These are all part of the story motif that comes from the use of the word “stories”.

Another lexical item that seems to reoccur in Hughes’ poetry is “song” or music. The reader is confronted with these items as he/she reads “The Negro Mother” and “Drum”. In Africa which is the aboriginal root of the African Americans, songs and music are used as media of cultural propagation, criticism, etc. hence we hear the persona in “the Negro Mother” say:

But God put a song and a prayer in my mouth.
God put a dream like steel in my soul.
Now through my children, I’m reaching the goal.
Now through my children, young and free,

I realize the blessings denied to me

The song that God puts in her mouth is loaded with the messages that help her to attain her goals vicariously through her children. These songs are what have helped her to swim through “the valley... filled with tears” in the past. Furthermore, in “Drum”, the poet-persona tells his audience to “bear in mind/ that death is a drum/ beating forever. The use of the lexeme “drum” is very implicative. Drums in Africa are means of communicating important messages. The use of this word here is intended to tell the Africans that the message is a very important one as it will call forth life for them. Hence, “Death is a drum,/ a signal drum,/ calling life/ to come!”. In conclusion, just like the reader observes in the poetry of Paul Laurence Dunbar, in Langston Hughes’ poetry, there is a deliberateness in the choices of lexical items towards the assertion of the African American distinct identity.

Conclusion

From the foregoing, the reader can observe that the utilization of Ebonics by Paul Laurence Dunbar is actually a resistance to the racial hegemony the usage of the standard American English may impose on the African American. Hence, his usage of Ebonics is to allow the African American artists the creative space to express their distinct idiosyncrasies and nuances. Furthermore, Hughes’ diction and lexical choices, though very simple and seemingly straight forward, are pregnant with deep metaphors and racial implications. These implications are targeted at destroying the racial bottlenecks that were enshrined by the racial white and aimed at keeping the Blacks in servitude perpetually.

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